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THE EVALUATION OF RATIONAL USE OF ANTIBIOTICS IN TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the study is to evaluate the rational use of antibiotics among patients in a tertiary care teaching hospital. A prospective observational study was conducted, in which the antibiotic prescriptions in the medicine department were analysed. 128 case records of patients were identified and evaluated for the rational use of antibiotics for a period of 6 months. Overall 1269 drugs were prescribed in 128 prescriptions, out of which 287(22.62%) were antibiotics. Out of 128 prescriptions, there were 105(36.59%) Cephalosporins, 41(14.29%) Penicillins, 29(10.10%) Macrolides, 25(8.71%) Fluoroquinolones, 19(6.62%) Tetracyclines, 17(5.92%) Metronidazole, 11(3.83%) Aminoglycosides, 10(3.48%) Carbapenems, 7(2.45%) Lincosamides, 5(1.74%) Nitrofurantoin, 5(1.74%) Azoles, 4(1.39%) Sulphonamides, 3(1.05%) Rifamycins, 3(1.05%) Oxazolidones, 2(0.70%) Albendazole and 1(0.35%) Glycopeptides. 39(30.47%) prescriptions were prescribed with single antibiotic, 46(35.94%) and 25(19.53%) prescriptions were respectively prescribed with 2 and 3 antibiotics, 13(10.15%) prescriptions were prescribed with 4 antibiotics and 5(3.91%) prescriptions were prescribed with >4 antibiotics. 79(61.72%) prescriptions were rational and 49(38.28%) prescriptions were irrational. Out of 128 cases, 113(88.28%) were empirical, 9(7.03%) were prophylactic and 6(4.69%) were definite therapy. Prescriptions were analysed and rationality of prescriptions were assessed for parameters such as untreated condition, duplication of therapeutic group, inappropriate drug, contraindication, treatment without indication and inappropriate dose, duration and frequency of antibiotics respectively. Thus the study concludes that 61.72% of prescriptions were rational.

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INTRODUCTION

Antibiotics are substances that inhibit the growth of or destroy microorganisms, without causing harm to the host. These are either natural (produced by microorganisms) or synthetic (prepared in the laboratory)[14]. Antibiotics were known as “miracle drugs” after their initial introduction in the 1940s[25]. These are the drugs that either kill or inhibit the growth of bacteria: bactericidal and bacteriostatic respectively[10].

Antibiotics can be either broad spectrum or narrow spectrum.

• Broad spectrum antibiotics :

The broad spectrum antibiotics are active against many types of microbes such as bacteria, rickettsia, mycoplasmas, protozoa and spirochetes. E.g: Penicillin

• Narrow spectrum antibiotics :

Narrow spectrum antibiotics are the one which are active against certain types of bacteria. E.g: Isoniazid[14].

The use of antibiotics has become a routine practice for the treatment of illnesses. The frequent use of broad spectrum antibiotics has led to the emergence of microbial resistance. These contribute towards the rapid rise of health care costs and patient morbidity and mortality[21].

RATIONALITY OF ANTIBIOTICS

Rational use of antibiotics requires that the patient receives right antibiotics in the right dose for the right duration as appropriate to their clinical needs at the lowest cost (WHO 1988) [12].

The irrational use of antibiotics are the most controversial and debated issue in today's clinical practice. It is a global problem especially in developing countries resulting in an increased microbial resistance leading to higher cost of treatment, prolonged hospitalization and adverse drug reaction(ADR)[1].

The antibiotic usage have remarkably brought down mortality and morbidity from communicable diseases. Simultaneously, inappropriate use of antibiotics is widespread all over the world. Even for trivial infections of viral etiology, an increasing trend is noticed for use of combinations, broad spectrum and newer generation antibiotics[20].

IRRATIONAL USE OF ANTIBIOTICS

Drugs are “doubled edged swords”. Indiscriminate use of antibiotics expands the cost of the medical treatment as well as increases the morbidity and mortality[15]. The outcome of irrational use of antibiotics includes economic loss, development of adverse drug reactions and development of antimicrobial resistance[8].

The use of antibiotics for viral infections, unnecessary prescribing of broad spectrums, use of inappropriate doses and durations, patient self treatments etc leads to antibiotic resistance and ineffective treatment [9].

The main types of irrationalities in drug usage include over prescribing, under prescribing, incorrect prescribing, use of irrational harmful drug combinations and improper diagnosis[15].

The overuse and misuse of antibiotics can lead to significant consequences like increased cost, bacterial resistance, therapeutic failure, drug toxicities and drug interactions[4]. A knowledge on how antibacterial agents are being prescribed and used is fundamental to obtain a rational drug use[7].

Antibiotic resistance occurs when the micro-organism is resistant to an antibiotic spectrum. This is due to mutations in the genetic material of the microorganism by "contamination" of the organism with plasmids or other transposable elements. Every time an antibiotic is used, whether appropriately or not, in human being or in animals, the probability of development and spread of antibiotic-resistant bacteria is multiplied. The universal evolution of antibiotic resistance poses a serious threat to the health of patients because it results in increased morbidity and mortality[2]. Antibiotic resistance, a global problem is particularly seen in developing countries where the infectious disease burden is high and cost constrains the replacement of older antibiotics with newer and more expensive drugs[17]. As a result of resistance, infection fails to respond to standard treatment which results in prolonged illness and increase risk of death. Antibiotic resistance lead to the decreased effect of effective antibiotics and infection remains for prolonged period of time. When microorganisms become resistant to first line antibiotics, expensive antibiotics are prescribed which increases cost of the therapy and hospitalisation[13].

Now a days, it is a major issue confronting healthcare providers and patients. Changing antibiotic resistance patterns, rising antibiotic costs and the introduction of new antibiotics has made selection of optimal antibiotic regimens more difficult. Further, history has taught us that if we do not use antibiotics wisely, they will lose their efficacy[16]. The inappropriate and overuse of antibiotics are the major contributing factors to the emergence of bacterial resistance globally. The problem is further aggravated by self-medication and non-therapeutic use of antibiotics by individuals without the guidance of a qualified healthcare providers[19]. Therefore, it is necessary to provide awareness to the patients about the rational use of antibiotics. The rational prescribing skills of clinicians can be assessed by conducting periodic prescription audits. It is necessary to ensure that the patients are always given evidence-based, cost-effective and rational treatments. The rational use of antibiotics is being significantly considered as an important contribution to control the worldwide emergence of bacterial resistance, to minimize the side effects and to reduce the cost of the treatment[7].

Failure to conduct microbiological testing is the main reason for incorrect antibiotic therapy. Cultures and susceptibility testings are essential to confirm the appropriateness of empirical therapy or redirecting therapy in a safe and effective manner, so that it actually targets the causative agent of the infection[18].

Antibiotic guidelines are standard set of instructions for the treatment of infectious diseases based on local culture sensitivity data. These guidelines help the physician to prescribe the antibiotics rationally. Thus encouraging the rational use of antibiotics would definitely help mankind to fight the disease and the illness for a better tomorrow[22].

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

Prospective Observational Study.

Ethical Issues

The ethical clearance for the study was acquired from the institutional ethical committee of Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere.

Methods

A prospective observational study was carried out in the Medicine department of a tertiary care teaching hospital at Davangere for six months with a sample size of 128 patients. The inclusion criteria involved patients of either sex, patient admitted for more than 2 days in medicine ward and prescription with atleast one antibiotic. Exclusion criteria involved patients who are treated from outpatient department, patients below 18 years of age, patients who are not willing to provide informed consent and patients with missing and insufficient data.

Data will be collected from case sheets of inpatients who are admitted in the Medicine department. The first phase of the study included preparation of a data collection form which comprises of patient demographics, present complaints, length of hospitalization, relevant previous medical and medication history and details of medications prescribed during hospitalization. In the second phase, the collected data from the patient profile was categorized, assessed and analysed for the parameters such as antibiotic irrationality and to identify the most common antibiotic class prescribed.

A computerized database was created by using Microsoft Excel Sheet and all details of the patients and datas were enrolled into it. The collected data was analysed.

RESULTS

Out of 128 prescriptions, a total of 1269 drugs were prescribed. Out of which 287(22.62%) were antibiotics and drugs other than antibiotics were 982(77.38%) (fig.1). Among the total prescriptions, 46(35.94%) prescriptions had two antibiotics followed by 39(30.47%) prescriptions had one antibiotic, 25(19.53%) prescriptions had three antibiotic, 13(10.15%) prescriptions had four antibiotics and 5(3.91%) prescriptions had more than 4 antibiotics (table.1). Out of 128 cases, 113(88.28%) were empirical, 9(7.03%) were prophylactic and 6(4.69%) were definite therapy(table.2). Among 287 antibiotics prescribed, the mostly prescribed antibiotics were Cephalosporin 105 (36.59%) than other class of antibiotics such as Beta-lactum antibiotics 48(16.72%), Macrolides 29(10.10%), Fluoroquinolone 25(8.71%), Tetracycline 19(6.62%), Metronidazole 17(5.92%), Amino glycosides 11(3.83%), Carbapenems 10(3.48%), Lincosamides 7(2.45%) (table.3). Among 105 cephalosporin antibiotics, ceftriaxone 72(68.57%) was most commonly prescribed followed by cefixime 9(8.57%), cefoperazone 8(7.62%), cefotaxime 7(6.67%), cefuroxime 6(5.71%) and ceftazidime 3(2.86%). Among cephalosporin antibiotics, 2nd generation (cefuroxime) and 3rd generation (ceftriaxone, cefixime, cefoperazone, cefotaxime and ceftazidime) were prescribed (table.4). From 128 prescriptions included in the study, 79(61.72%) prescriptions were rational and 49(38.28%) were found to be irrational (table.5). Out of 73 irrationalities, 22(30.13%) were inappropriate antibiotic, 12(16.44%) were antibiotic duplication, 2(2.74%) were contraindicated antibiotic, 9(12.33%) were treatment without indication, 2(2.74%) were low dose, 4(5.48%) were high dose, 17(23.29%) were short duration, 3(4.11%) were long duration, 2(2.74%) antibiotics were given with inappropriate frequency and there were no untreated indication (table.6).

Figure 1: Number of drugs prescribed.

Table 1: Number Of Antibiotics Per Prescription.

NUMBER OF ANTIBIOTICS PER PRESCRIPTION	FREQUENCY (n=128)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	39	30.47
2	46	35.94
3	25	19.53
4	13	10.15
>4	5	3.91
TOTAL	128	100

Table 2: Antibiotic therapy.

TYPE OF THERAPY	NUMBER OF PRESCRIPTION (n=128)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Empirical	113	88.28
Prophylactic	09	7.03
Definite therapy	06	4.69
TOTAL	128	100

Table 3: Commonly Prescribed Antibiotics Class.

ANTIBIOTIC CLASS	NUMBER OF ANTIBIOTICS (n=287)	PERCENTAGE(%)
Cephalosporins	105	36.59
Beta lactum(penicillins)	48	16.72
Macrolides	29	10.10
Fluoroquinolones	25	8.71
Tetracyclines	19	6.62
Metronidazole	17	5.92
Aminoglycosides	11	3.83
Carbapenems	10	3.48
Lincosamides	7	2.45
Nitrofurantoin	5	1.74
Sulphonamides	4	1.39
Rifamycins	3	1.05
Oxazolidones	3	1.05
Glycopeptides	1	0.35
TOTAL	287	100

Table 4: Cephalosporin Antibiotics.

CEPHALOSPORIN ANTIBIOTIC	FREQUENCY (n=105)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Ceftriaxone	72	68.57
Cefixime	09	8.57
Cefoperazone	08	7.62
Cefotaxime	07	6.67
Cefuroxime	06	5.71
Ceftazidime	03	2.86
TOTAL	105	100

Table 5 : Rationality of prescriptions.

RATIONALITY	NUMBER OF PRESCRIPTION (n=128)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Rational	79	61.72
Irrational	49	38.28
TOTAL	128	100

Table 6: Parameters for Irrationality.

PARAMETERS FOR IRRATIONALITY	FREQUENCY (n=73)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Untreated Indication	0	0
Inappropriate Antibiotics	22	30.13
Antibiotic Duplication	12	16.44
Contraindicated Antibiotics	2	2.74
Treatment Without Indication	9	12.33
Low Dose	2	2.74
High Dose	4	5.48
Short Duration	17	23.29
Long Duration	3	4.11
Frequency of antibiotics	2	2.74
TOTAL	73	100

DISCUSSION

In our study, total of 1269 drugs were prescribed, out of which 287(22.62%) drugs were antibiotics. In study conducted by Rajesh S Hiray et al[3], out of 691 drugs 122 were antibiotics, which is similar to our result.

Out of 128 prescriptions, 39(30.47%) prescription contain 1 antibiotic, 46(35.94%) prescription contain 2 antibiotics, 25(19.53%) prescription contain 3 antibiotics, 13(10.15%) prescription contain 4 antibiotics and 5(3.91%) prescription contain more than 4 antibiotics. Similar results were found in the study conducted by Duo-shuang Xie et al[2] and Hanmant Amane et al[6].

Out of 128 prescription, 113(88.28%) prescriptions were empirical, 9(7.03%) prescriptions were prophylactic and 6(4.69%) prescriptions were definite therapy. Same results were observed in study conducted by Ozlem Tunger et al[5], which shows that 167(71.4%) prescriptions were empirical, 56(23.9%) prescriptions were prophylactic and 11(4.7%) were definite therapy.

Out of 287 antibiotics prescribed, the mostly preferred Antibiotics was Cephalosporin 105(36.59%) than other class of antibiotics such as B-lactam antibiotics 48(16.72%), Macrolides 29(10.10%), Fluoroquinolone 25(8.71%), Tetracycline 19(6.62%), Metronidazole 17(5.92%), Aminoglycosides 11(3.83%), Carbapenems 10(3.48%), Lincosamides 7(2.45%). Cephalosporins were widely prescribed due to their broad spectrum of activity and tolerance across age groups. In studies conducted by P. Maheshwari et al[10] and B.Rajalingam et al[1], Cephalosporins were mostly prescribed, which resembles our study.

Out of 128 prescriptions, 79 are found to be rational and 49 were found to be irrational which include treatment without indication 9(12.33%), dose 6(8.22%), duration 20(27.40%) and frequency 2(2.74%). Results were identical in the study conducted by B. Rajalingam et al[1].

Other irrationalities include antibiotic duplication 12(16.44%), contraindicated antibiotic 2(2.74%) and inappropriate antibiotic 22(30.13%).

CONCLUSION

Analysing the prescription enlightens the way towards rational use of drugs. Irrational drug use leads to ineffective, unsafe treatment, prolongation of illness, distress and harm to patients.

In our study, a total of 128 cases were collected, of which the most commonly prescribed antibiotics were cephalosporins (3rd generation) followed by beta-lactam antibiotics.

Among 128 prescriptions 79 prescriptions were rational and 49 prescriptions were irrational, in which we identified 73 irrationalities, out of that 22(16.44%) inappropriate antibiotics was prescribed.

The active participation of clinical pharmacists in the clinical ward rounds and medication chart review can ensure rational prescribing of drugs and reduce the incidence of medication errors and adverse drug reactions. It will also reduce the cost of therapy which will ultimately benefit the patients.

Thus we conclude, this study provide insights for the rational use of antibiotics among patients and create awareness about proper use of antibiotics.

Further research should be designed to intervene the rationality of antibiotics and to evaluate the ways of responding to the antibiotic resistance challenges such as the development of novel strategies in the search for new antimicrobials and designing more effective preventive measures.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest

ABBREVIATIONS

ADR	Adverse Drug Reaction
CARAT	Council for Appropriate and Rational Antibiotic Therapy
WHO	World Health Organisation

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